

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, March- 2023 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 2764-9733 | ijersearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10104806

SYSTEMATIZED BIBLIOGRAPHIC REVIEW: GENERAL COMPETENCIES OF THE NURSE PRECEPTOR FOR THE PRACTICE OF UNDERGRADUATE CURRICULAR INTERNSHIP

AUTHORS

Camila Cristina Rodrigues (profcamilacristinarodrigues@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

Objective: To identify in the literature the competencies of the nurse preceptor for monitoring the supervised curricular internship in undergraduate nursing. Methodology: Systematized bibliographic review analyzed in light of the national curricular guidelines for undergraduate nursing described in CNE/CES Resolution No. 3 of November 7, 2001. Results and discussions: 451 articles were retrieved, and one study was analyzed that was related to the competence of the preceptor in primary care, referenced in the DNC/ENF in the health care item. Conclusion: The different studies confirmed our initial hypothesis that the general competences are included in the profile of the graduate in nursing. The different studies used synonyms to describe the competences, which can lead to variations in interpretation.